

GAME-BASED TEACHING OF PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS IN MUSIC LESSONS

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Abstract. *Competences of elementary school students in music lessons were analyzed based on games, primary school students through games.*

Keywords: *Music lessons, primary education students, competence, game technologies.*

National self-awareness of a person, thinking in the spirit of patriotism, high morale and formation of civic qualities is one of the main directions of the country's priority strategy and education policy. The rich national heritage of the Uzbek people, which has various genres, forms, styles and performance characteristics, in particular, folklore, serves as a fundamental basis and solid platform [1].

Students' musical-aesthetic competences are improved on the basis of diagnostic methods of self-evaluation indicators and emotional, figurative expressive-aesthetic gymnastic exercise sequence. As mentioned above, a person's national self-awareness is one of the factors that indicate the effectiveness of education in the higher education system. A person's self-awareness serves as the basis for self-evaluation. Self-awareness, self-evaluation feature is formed in the process of interaction with other people, during joint activities. First of all, he should learn that he has some qualities of ability [2].

Work on oneself and self-development are important in the development of the editor's professional competence. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-assessment. So, self-development is a conscious activity of a person that encourages him to fully realize himself as a person. Self-development implies a clear understanding of the goals of activity and its existence, ideals and personality [3].

It is envisaged that the integrative use of the diagnostic methods of self-assessment indicators will be used in the work. The concept of "curriculum" has a wide scope and has the following content: students' training aimed at finding, researching and solving problems, formalizing the result in the form of a tangible (material or intellectual) product, intended for the general consumer. method of organizing independent educational activity [4].

In the development of musical-aesthetic competences in general high school students, it is important to ensure the progressive dynamism of teaching principles, such as self-evaluation of professional competences, as well as content-emotional interpretation of musical concepts. In the development of students' musical-aesthetic competences, the gradual dynamic of teaching principles was assumed to be a gradual, gradual, evolutionary [5].

In the modern editorial technology, it is envisaged to develop and apply the methodological bases, specific mechanisms, methods of diagnosing the educational process and implementing the used theories, educational-methodical complexes based on experience and testing, using the editorial diagnostic methods.

The basis of the use of diagnostic methods is the formation and development of positive qualities and qualities in each person based on his needs, interests, talents and possibilities.

Their characteristics and tasks were taken into account when determining the sequence of use of emotional, expressive and rhythmic gymnastic exercises in the development of students' musical-aesthetic skills. Emotional is listening to music of a certain character, feeling the music, tightening its rhythm, or performing a rhythmic exercise. Image expression means that during the lesson, the student is given an image and the student must perform a rhythmic exercise that represents this image. For example, one can cite the songs of rowers, rowers and workers in the book "Work and rhythm" [57] by Karl Bucher. Emotional exercises are the expression of the character of music with a specific character or lyrical tone through rhythmic exercises. For example, we can cite R.Chowkovsky's piece "Kid's album" for forteriano.

The concept of game technology is a component of pedagogical technology. Game technology differs from the game method in traditional education by its clear goal, logical sequence and interdependence of the processes to be implemented, guarantee of achieving predetermined results.

In any technology, including game technologies, it is necessary to clearly define the learning goal. This is the core of the technology. In order for the goal to be set correctly, the educator must know what he wants to teach the child. It is advisable to set one goal in one training session. For example, introducing children to the number 3 or giving an understanding of the seasons, etc.

Game technologies (especially for kindergarten children) have developmental goals (development of the child's perception, memory, attention, thinking) is also possible. In this case, the final result is more important during the game.

Game technology also differs from the game method in its clear goal, logical sequence and interdependence of the processes to be implemented, and the guarantee of achieving predetermined results.

Pedagogical games can be classified as follows.

- Depending on the types of activity: social intellectual, labor, social and psychological games;
- Depending on the nature of pedagogical processes: educational, developmental, productive, creative, psychotechnical games.
- Depending on the methods of games: object, subject, artistic role-playing, imagining and dramatizing events.
- Games based on subjects: mathematical, biological, ecological, musical, technical, physical training, games that develop economic saving and business acumen, entrepreneurship.
- According to game tools: games with game tools (ball, pyramid, cube, etc.) and games without game tools, games played on the couch, in the room and in the field technical tools such as games, computer and television games.

In pre-school education, in the process of instilling the experience of older adults into younger ones, games appear as an educational method.

Based on the tasks of preschool education, based on the methods of play, subject-oriented, action-oriented, dramatized games are widely used.

The use of developmental pedagogical games in preschool education in the educational process will have the following specific character.

- First, developmental pedagogical games consist of a set of special tasks.

- Secondly, the tasks in the game are carried out using colored cubes, bricks, squares, plastic, cardboard, constructor-mechanical complexes with the help of various ornaments, pictures and silent subjects.

It is necessary to use rhythmic gymnastics exercises in the development of students' musical-aesthetic skills. In this, the teacher gives rhythmic gymnastics without the accompaniment of music and instruments.

In the development of students' musical and aesthetic competences, the issue of organization of movement forms is raised based on the study of Uzbek dances, their regional peculiarities and free movement forms that represent the individualization of the individual in the context of the general purpose of the movement. The research focuses on the history and established genres of Uzbek folklore heritage, the music of composers, and the practical exercises used in the editorial practice of famous teachers of our country.

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